

Solvent degradation & influences on amine-based carbon capture operations

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ABSTRACT

Amine-based carbon capture is one of the most widely used technologies for mitigating industrial CO₂ emissions. However, solvent degradation significantly compromises process efficiency and economic viability. This review critically examines both thermal and oxidative degradation mechanisms, emphasizing how operational conditions, such as flue gas composition, CO₂ loading, temperature, and pressure, influence degradation. The catalytic role of dissolved metals in oxidative degradation and the interconnection with corrosion is an important aspect of solvent degradation. Beyond chemical mechanisms, practical mitigation strategies including the use of inhibitors, solvent reclamation methods, and solvent selection criteria are discussed in detail. The limitations of current degradation monitoring techniques are also evaluated, emphasizing the need for real-time analytical solutions.

This review fills in a critical gap in the literature. While previous review papers provide a strong foundation on solvent degradation, this review goes a step further by focusing on the industrial implications and practical mitigation strategies. In addition to summarizing key degradation pathways, special attention is given to the role of metals in accelerating oxidative degradation through autocatalytic effects. This work also highlights how these mechanisms impact long-term solvent stability and operational efficiency. By covering both chemical insights and real-world challenges, this review aims to bridge the gap between laboratory findings and industrial application.

1. Introduction

The concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere continues to rise, currently at 422 ppm, with projections suggesting the concentration could exceed 500 ppm by 2050, in the scenario where no significant changes to current practices or policies take place (Unmitigated monthly global atmospheric, 2024). This underscores the urgent need for effective CO₂ mitigation technologies (Schwalm et al., 2020). Amine-based carbon capture remains one of the most developed and widely researched approaches in carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) (Unmitigated monthly global atmospheric, 2024). As this chemical carbon capture (CC) technique can be relatively easily retrofitted into existing industrial equipment, it is in use in power plants, biogas facilities and the cement production industry (CASPER, 2024, Tech Carbon capture, 2024).

Despite its widespread use, amine-based carbon capture presents several challenges that need to be addressed. One major issue is the high energy demand for solvent regeneration. A reboiler consumes typically

around 4 MJ/kg CO₂ or 1.11 kWh/kg CO₂ for a classical MEA system (Oi and Kvam, 2014). Given an average CO₂ emission of 0.1 - 1 kg CO₂/kWh, this significant energy requirement reduces the overall carbon capture efficiency (Carbon intensity, 2024, Greenhouse gas, 2025). Thus, there is a pressing need for more energy-efficient process configurations.

Secondly, solvent degradation has gained increasingly more attention in recent years due to its importance in the operation of a carbon capture plant. Solvent degradation occurs when solvent degrades to a point where it cannot be effectively regenerated in the stripper column. An example of a fresh solvent sample and a degraded solvent sample can be seen in Fig. 1. A visible colour change took place due to the presence of degradation products.

Solvent degradation diminishes overall capture capacity, increases energy consumption, can damage equipment, induces corrosion, and is responsible for a big amount of solvent loss making it highly undesirable in any scenario (Fytianos et al., 2016, Ling et al., 2019, Supap et al., 2011, Huang et al., 2014). Experiments at the CO₂ Technology Centre Mongstad in Norway showed that after 1,960 h of operation, a solvent

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Fig. 1. Image of a fresh solvent sample (left) and a degraded solvent sample (right).

loss of 1.6 kg MEA per ton of captured CO₂ was observed (Morken et al., 2017). Of the total loss, 83 % was due to solvent degradation, with 67 % attributed to NH₃ emissions and 16 % to other degradation products. With an MEA cost of \$1.10 per kilogram, solvent degradation results in an additional solvent cost of \$1.76 per ton of CO₂ captured (Ding et al., 2023). While this may seem minor, large-scale carbon capture plants, such as the Petra Nova facility in Texas, capture over 1 million tons of CO₂ annually, leading to a substantial cost from solvent loss due to solvent degradation (Panja et al., 2022). Overall, solvent degradation negatively impacts both the economic and environmental aspects of carbon capture, highlighting the need for further research and monitoring (Vega et al., 2014).

The primary objective of this review paper is to provide a comprehensive analysis of solvent degradation in chemical carbon capture (CC) installations, with a particular focus on the industrial consequences and

mitigation strategies. It covers the underlying mechanisms of degradation, identification and characterization of degradation products, and their impact on long-term solvent performance and plant efficiency. The review includes both conventional amines, such as monoethanolamine (MEA) and diethanolamine (DEA), and newer blends like the CESARI solvent, which contains 2-amino-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ). Key aspects such as thermal and oxidative degradation, the role of flue gas impurities, and the autocatalytic effects of metals are discussed in detail (Hume et al., 2021). The paper also highlights practical challenges, and explores promising developments and future directions to improve solvent management and overall process sustainability.

2. Amine-based carbon capture

Amine-based carbon capture, also known as amine scrubbing, is a well-established technique for capturing CO₂. In this section, a brief description of a typical amine-based CO₂ capture unit is provided.

The amine-based CO₂ capture process is shown in Fig. 2. The green lines in Fig. 2 represent liquid streams and blue lines are the gas streams. Flue gas containing CO₂ enters the absorber from the bottom (see (1) in Fig. 2), while a lean amine solvent is introduced from the top (see (2) in Fig. 2). The CO₂ reacts with the amine in a counter-current flow. Where primary and secondary amines react directly with CO₂ to form amine-carbonates and bicarbonates represented by Reactions 1 and 2 respectively.

R₂ represents a hydrogen atom in the case of primary amines and a carbonyl group for secondary amines (Couchaux et al., 2014, Dutcher et al., 2015).

Tertiary amines do not react directly with CO₂. Instead, tertiary amines catalyse the hydration of CO₂ to form bicarbonate ions. Acting as a base, the tertiary amine accepts a proton from a water molecule, which facilitates the reaction as illustrated in Reaction 3 (Couchaux et al., 2014, Dutcher et al., 2015).

Fig. 2. Graphical overview of an amine-based carbon capture setup.

The CO₂-loaded solvent, now containing carbamates or bicarbonates, is heated in a heat exchanger (see (3) in Fig. 2) and sent to the top of the stripper (see (4) in Fig. 2). Here, the solvent is exposed to steam produced by the reboiler (see (5) in Fig. 2). The addition of heat energy reverses the reactions shown earlier, releasing the CO₂ from the amine. The CO₂ and uncondensed steam then move to the condenser (see (6) in Fig. 2), where the two are separated. The regenerated amine is cooled in the heat exchanger and possibly further cooled by a secondary cooler (see (7) in Fig. 2) before being recycled back to the absorber (Van Wagener et al., 2014, Liang et al., 2015).

One of the key challenges in amine-based carbon capture is reducing both energy consumption and solvent degradation, which are closely related. Solvent degradation often requires more advanced process configurations, including wash towers, acid wash sections, and reclaiming systems. Lighter contaminants such as hydrocarbons, ammonia (NH₃), and hydrogen cyanide (HCN) accumulate in the reflux stream and are usually purged to keep their levels under control. Heavier contaminants, including degradation products, heat-stable salts (HSS), and corrosion products, build up in the circulating amine solution. These heavier compounds can cause fouling on heat exchangers and trays, and their removal typically involves costly treatments such as bleed and feed, ion exchange, or thermal reclamation, in addition to particle filtration. Solvent degradation mechanisms and the different solvent degradation products will be discussed in the next section.

3. Solvent degradation mechanisms

Solvent degradation does not only lead to solvent loss, it can also cause fouling, increase corrosion rates, foaming and solvent disposal (Vega et al., 2014). In classical MEA-based carbon capture systems, solvent makeup accounts for approximately 10% of the total cost of the CO₂ capture unit (Rao and Rubin, 2002). To reduce costs, it is essential to minimize solvent degradation. A first step to achieve this is to better understand the degradation mechanisms.

Amine degradation can generally be divided into two main categories: thermal degradation and oxidative degradation. Where thermal degradation is the degradation due to thermal stress in the presence of CO₂. Oxidative degradation is degradation that is induced due to the presence of oxygen, oxygen containing compounds, and metals (Vega et al., 2014, Lepaumier et al., 2009, Campbell et al., 2022).

3.1. Thermal degradation

Thermal degradation refers to the breakdown of chemical solvents, such as amines used in CO₂ capture, due to high temperatures. This process can lead to the formation of unwanted by-products, reduced solvent efficiency, and increased operational costs (Zoannou et al., 2013). Thermal degradation primarily occurs in the stripper (red region, Fig. 2), where temperatures range between 100 and 150 °C (Vega et al., 2014). This range is broad because different solvents have varying thermal stabilities and begin to degrade at different temperatures, as discussed in the following section. Key factors influencing thermal degradation include the stripper pressure, solvent concentration, and CO₂ loading (Neerup et al., 2023).

3.1.1. Thermal degradation mechanisms

Different amines degrade through a variety of pathways, with several mechanisms identified to explain the degradation of commonly used amines, including primary, secondary, and tertiary alkanolamines, di-amines, cyclic amines, and their various derivatives. This section provides an overview of the key degradation mechanisms for the most widely used amine structures. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for comparing solvent stability, as the structural differences between solvents directly influence their degradation behaviour. This

foundation will support later discussions on why some solvents are more stable than others and how their structures impact degradation pathways.

3.1.1.1. Primary and secondary alkanol amines. Carbamate polymerization is a common degradation mechanism for shorter primary and secondary alkanolamines, such as ethanol- and propanol-based amines. This process occurs through multiple steps, which are illustrated using MEA in Fig. 3(a).

First, the alkanolamine reacts with CO₂ to form carbamate (Step (1) in Fig. 3(a)). The carbamate then undergoes a cyclization reaction, losing water (dehydrolysis), and forming an oxazolidinone (OZD) (Step (2) in Fig. 3(a)). Subsequently, an unreacted alkanolamine can attack the ketone group from either side, leading to the formation of a dimer (Step (3) in Fig. 3(a)) or an alkanolamine urea (Step (4) in Fig. 3(a)). Additionally, the resulting dimer can undergo cyclization to form an imidazolidinone (Step (5) in Fig. 3(a)) (Huang et al., 2014, Rochelle, May 2012, Davis, Oct. 23, 2024, Lepaumier et al., 2025). The key distinction between oxazolidinones and imidazolidinones lies in their stability. Oxazolidinones are highly reactive and readily convert into other products, while imidazolidinones are stable and tend to accumulate (Lepaumier et al., 2009).

Additionally, more complex degradation products can form through a series of nucleophilic and cyclization reactions. An example of this process is shown for MEA in Fig. 3(b). The dimer can attack the oxazolidinone, resulting in the formation of a trimer component (see (1) in Fig. 3(b)). Finally, the trimer can react with CO₂ and undergo cyclization, forming a cyclic urea (see (2) in Fig. 3(b)). This polymerization reaction can theoretically continue, producing increasingly larger compounds. Up to quaternary MEA components have even been identified in degradation experiments (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).

3.1.1.2. Transalkylation of tertiary alkanol amines. As mentioned in Section 2 tertiary amines do not react directly with CO₂, but act as a catalyst. An example of how this reaction proceeds for di-ethyl ethanol amine (DEEA) is shown in (1) in Fig. 4 (Gao et al., 2015). In terms of degradation, a dealkylation reaction of the protonated tertiary amine can result in the formation of a dialkylamine and ethylene oxide. This reaction is shown in (2) in Fig. 4 for the protonated DEEA (Lepaumier et al., 2009, Gao et al., 2015).

Tertiary amines can also degrade through transalkylation (a secondary nucleophilic substitution, S_N2 reaction) and elimination. For the transalkylation, a tertiary amine can attack a protonated tertiary amine (Step (3) in Fig. 4). This results in the transfer of an alkyl group from one to the other, leading to the formation of a secondary amine and a quaternary amine (Lepaumier et al., 2009, Gao et al., 2015). The secondary amine can then undergo further degradation as discussed in Fig. 3. The main degradation products are subsequently formed through carbamate formation, ring closing, and ring opening via the formed secondary amine as previously described in Fig. 3 (Rochelle, May 2012, Gao et al., 2015). However, tertiary dimers, in contrast to secondary dimers, can form other compounds besides imidazolidinones and cyclic urea (Fig. 3) as result of the polymerization reaction. A tertiary dimer can also undergo a cyclization reaction to form piperazines (Lepaumier et al., 2009, Gao et al., 2015).

Furthermore, in alkaline environments an additional pathway for the quaternary amine is proposed. A reaction occurs where the quaternary amine forms both a trialkyl amine and an alkylene glycol, as can be seen in (4) in Fig. 4 (Gao et al., 2015).

Understanding the degradation mechanisms of tertiary amines, such as DEEA, provides valuable insights into their behaviour in CO₂ capture systems and helps explain their relative stability compared to other amine types. These degradation pathways: dealkylation, transalkylation, and polymerization reactions show the complexity of tertiary amine degradation.

Fig. 3. (a) Thermal degradation mechanism for MEA (b) Polymerization reaction of MEA degradation products.

Fig. 4. Thermal degradation pathway of DEEA.

3.1.1.3. Degradation of diamines: ethylene diamines and propylene diamines. Overall diamines degrade very similar to alkanolamines as previously discussed. However, there are some small differences and things to point out. First, a distinction must be made between III–III, III–II, or III–I diamines. Where the roman ciphers indicate the amount of alkyl groups that are attached to the nitrogen atoms (Lepaumier et al., 2009). This is illustrated in Fig. 5(a), where a III–III shows an amine where both nitrogen atoms contain three (III) alkyl groups. In contrast to the III–I configured amine, where there is only one (I) alkyl group present on the second nitrogen.

In general, the degradation of ethylene diamines leads to the formation of mostly oligomers and cyclic compounds, similar to the degradation of alkanolamines (Thompson et al., 2017). However, for III–III ethylene diamines a dealkylation is necessary to initiate further degradation of the diamine. As a consequence III–III are less prone to degradation than other types of diamines (Lepaumier et al., 2009, Thompson et al., 2017). Overall diamine stability can be ordered from most stable to least stable as following: III–III > III–I > III–II > II–II (Lepaumier et al., 2009).

Propylene diamines degrade differently compared to other diamines, as addition reactions and ring closures are not favourable in this case. This is illustrated for trimethyl-propyl diamine (TMPDA) in Fig. 5(b) (Lepaumier et al., 2009, Lepaumier et al., 2025). In general methylation and demethylation of the amine can occur, so an alkyl group is added or removed from the amine (see (1) in Fig. 5(b)) (Lepaumier et al., 2009). A direct Hofmann elimination reaction can also take place resulting in the

formation of allylamine and trimethylamine (see (2) in Fig. 5(b)) (Lepaumier et al., 2025).

Understanding the degradation pathways of diamines provides a basis for evaluating their stability and suitability for carbon capture applications. The difference in degradation behaviour between ethylene and propylene diamines highlights the importance of structural factors in determining degradation products and -resistance.

3.1.1.4. Example: degradation of piperazine. PZ is a cyclic secondary diamine that has a high CO_2 absorption capacity of 0.51 g CO_2 per gram piperazine (Gupta et al., 2022). The high absorption capacity is one of the reasons PZ is often used in solvent blends like the CESAR1 solvent. PZ is an increasingly used amine and will therefore be discussed separately.

The degradation of PZ is highly complex, with many mechanisms still not fully understood. Nonetheless, pathways have been proposed based on detected degradation products. Mazari et al. and Freeman et al. (Mazari et al., 2014, Freeman, 2024). have outlined degradation pathways to explain the formation of certain observed products. Key mechanisms include $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ reactions, elimination reactions, urea formation, and hydrogen abstraction. Due to its complexity, piperazine degradation has been the focus of several dedicated studies (Mazari et al., 2014, Freeman, 2024, Olaolu Alawode, 2024).

As illustrated in Fig. 6(a) the degradation of piperazine (PZ) begins with an initial reaction where a protonated PZ molecule (H^+PZ) attacks the α -carbon of an unreacted PZ molecule (see (1) in Fig. 6(a)) (Mazari

Fig. 5. (a) Example of different configured ethylene diamines (b) Degradation pathway for TMPDA.

et al., 2014). This results in the formation of 1- [2-[(2-aminoethyl) amino]ethyl] piperazine (AEAEPZ), a compound consisting of two segments: a piperazine group (see (2) in Fig. 6(a)) and an ethylenediamine (EDA) group (see (3) in Fig. 6(a)). In the presence of CO₂, AEAEPZ can undergo a reaction leading to the formation of an internal urea. The EDA segment within the AEAEPZ molecule essentially behaves like a dimer, ultimately forming an imidazolidinone via carbamate formation and cyclization (see (4) in Fig. 6(a)). Further S_N2 reactions can occur through various pathways. While PZ itself can act as a nucleophile, other degradation products can also drive S_N2 reactions, introducing additional degradation pathways. A frequently proposed reaction, (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024, Mazari et al., 2014), is an unreacted PZ molecule attacking the protonated urea of AEAEPZ, leading to the formation of a quintamine, ammonium, and CO₂ (see (5) in Fig. 6(a)).

Parks et al (Parks et al., 2021) have proposed additional degradation pathways based on the Density Functional Theory (DFT) (Density, 2024). DFT is employed to predict degradation products and mechanisms. One common degradation product of amines, including piperazine, is N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-imidazolidin-2-one (HEIA). A proposed pathway for HEIA formation is illustrated in Fig. 6(b) (Parks et al., 2021). In the first step, a piperazine carbonate forms a zwitterion in a chair configuration (Step (1) in Fig. 6(b)). Thermal energy then induces a conformational change from the chair to a boat configuration (Step (2) in Fig. 6(b)). Finally, a cyclization reaction results in the formation of HEIA (Step (3) in Fig. 6(b)).

Numerous other degradation pathways have been proposed, leading to the formation of various thermal products summarized in Table 1 (Parks et al., 2021). This table is an overview of the current understanding and there may be additional information available. A detailed discussion of all the possible theoretical degradation pathways and related products will be extensive and not within the scope of this work.

The details of the table are discussed later.

Looking into degradation mechanisms can give valuable insights in trying to prevent and regulate solvent degradation. The development of inhibitors can stem from the understanding of degradation mechanisms and can lead to improvements in solvent monitoring and control.

3.1.2. Thermal degradation products

Table 1 provides an overview of thermal degradation products formed in various amine-based solvents under different conditions. It shows that thermal degradation produces a wide range of products, including oxazolidinones, imidazolidinones, cyclic urea, and other more complex degradation products.

When degradation products are experimentally identified, the conditions of the experiment are included in the table, as these significantly influence the degradation process. In lab-based thermal degradation experiments, temperatures are often set higher than those encountered in industrial settings to speed up the degradation process. For example, Gao et al (Gao et al., 2015) conducted experiments at temperatures up to 175°C, which exceed the conditions typically found in industrial amine-based CO₂ capture processes (Løge et al., 2025).

The degradation behaviour varies considerably depending on factors such as solvent composition, temperature, CO₂ loading, and experiment duration. In experiments with a higher temperature or longer duration more and often more complex degradation products are formed than in experiments at lower temperatures or shorter durations. Different solvents lead to different degradation products. For instance, MEA-based systems typically produce HEEDA, HEIA, and oxazolidinones, while more complex amines, like piperazine systems, can result in products such as N-formyl piperazine, and AEP. Some of the degradation products listed in the Table 1 are well-established, while others remain more hypothetical due to the challenges in identifying them with current

Fig. 6. (a) Thermal degradation mechanism of piperazine (b) Formation of HEIA through a zwitterion complex.

analytical techniques.

Table 1 offers a summary of discovered degradation products for different solvents under various conditions, which can be useful for identifying potential degradation products in future experiments or studies. The table also mentions which analytical techniques are being used for the quantification or identification of the degradation products. Common techniques like gas chromatography (GC), Liquid

Chromatography (LC), High performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and Ion Chromatography (IC) are often used.

3.2. Oxidative degradation

In addition to thermal degradation, oxidative degradation plays an

Table 1
Overview of thermal degradation products discussed in literature.

Reference	Solvent	Degradation products	T [°C]	CO ₂ loading [mol CO ₂ /mol alkalinity]	Duration of degradation	Detection method
Campbell et al (Campbell et al., Nov. 25, 2022).	AMP	4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone DMOZD	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	GC, GC-FID
Thompson et al (Thompson et al., 2017).	2.5 m 1,2-DAP	4-methyl-2-imidazolidinone Urea component (Unidentified) Cyclic Di-urea C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ (Unidentified)	125-145	0.4	1 week	LC-TOF-MS
Thompson et al (Thompson et al., 2017).	2.5 m 1,3-DAP	Tetrahydro-2 (1H)-pyrimidinone N,N'-Bis (3-aminopropyl)-urea Cyclic Di-urea C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ (Unidentified)	125-145	0.4	1 week	LC-TOF-MS
Gao et al (Gao et al., 2015).	≈ 2-4 m DEEA	N-ethylethanamine (EEA) Triethylamine Ethylene glycol (EG) Diethylamine Ethylene oxide (EO) N-ethyloxazolidinone (EOZD) N,N-ethyl-N'-(2-hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine (DEHEED) N,N,N'-ethyl-ethylenediamine (TEED) N,N-diethylpiperazine (DEP) 3-ethyl-oxazolidine Dimethylol ethylene urea N,N,N',N'-tetraethyl-1,2-ethanediamine N-ethylmorpholine (EM) 1,3,5-triazine-1,3,5 (2H,4H,6H)-triethanol N,N,N',N'',N''-penta-ethyl diethylenetriamine	120-175	0.3-0.7	3 weeks	GC-MS
Thompson et al (Thompson et al., 2017).	2.5 m EDA	2-Imidazolidinone (IZD) N,N'-bis (2-aminoethyl)-urea (Urea) Cyclic Di-urea C ₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ (Unidentified)	125-145	0.4	1 week	LC-TOF-MS
Léonard et al (Léonard et al., 2014).	7 m MEA	N-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine (HEEDA) N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-imidazolidin-2-one (HEIA) 2-oxazolidinone (OZD)	140	0.4	3 weeks	HPLC, GC, FTIR
Davis J (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).	3.5 m –11 m MEA	Oxazolidinone MEA urea MEA dimer (HEEDA) Cyclic urea of MEA dimer (HEIA) MEA/HEEDA urea MEA trimer Cyclic urea of MEA trimer MEA quatramer Cyclic urea of MEA quatramer	100-150	0.2 –0.5	8 weeks	IC, HPLC, IC-MS, MS, GC
Davis J (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).	Blend 7m MEA/2m AMP	2-ethylenediamine-2-methyl-1-propanol N-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine (HEEDA) N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-imidazolidin-2-one (HEIA) Tri-HEIA	100-150	0.4	12 weeks	IC, HPLC, IC-MS, MS, GC
Davis J (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).	Blend 7m MEA/2m morpholine	4-morpholineethanamine 4-[2-[(2-aminoethyl)amino]ethyl]morpholine N-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine (HEEDA) N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-imidazolidin-2-one (HEIA) Tri-HEIA	100-150	0.4	12 weeks	IC, HPLC, IC-MS, MS, GC
Davis J (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).	Blend 7m MEA/2m PZ	N-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine (HEEDA) N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-imidazolidin-2-one (HEIA) Tri-HEIA N-(2-aminoethyl)piperazine (AEP) Ethylenediamine (EDA) 1,4-piperazinediethamine Piperazine urea	100-150	0.4	12 weeks	IC, HPLC, IC-MS, MS, GC
Thompson et al (Thompson et al., 2017).	2.5 m N-MEDA	1-methyl-2-imidazolidinone Urea component (Unidentified)	125-145	0.4	1 week	LC-TOF-MS

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Reference	Solvent	Degradation products	T [°C]	CO ₂ loading [mol CO ₂ /mol alkalinity]	Duration of degradation	Detection method
Freeman S (Freeman, 2024).	8 m PZ	Cyclic Di-urea C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ (Unidentified) 1,4-Dimethylpiperazine (1,4-DMPZ) 1-Ethylpiperazine (1-EPZ) 1-Methylpiperazine (1-MPZ) 2-Imidazolidone (2-Imid) 1-(2-aminoethyl)piperazine (AEP) Glycolate Oxalate Acetate Formate Ethylenediamine (EDA) 1-Formylpiperazine (FPZ) 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine (HEP)	165	0.3	20 weeks	IC, IC-MS, NMR, HPLC, LC-MS, AA-LC
Campbell et al (Campbell et al., Nov. 25, 2022).	PZ	N-formylpiperazine (FPZ) Ethylenediamine (EDA) Aminoethyl piperazine (AEP) Formate Ammonia	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	GC, GC-FID
Mazari et al (Mazari et al., 2014).	PZ	N-formylpiperazine (FPZ) Ethylenediamine (EDA) Aminoethyl piperazine (AEP) Ammonia	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	GC

N.A.: Not Applicable –degradation products mentioned based on theoretical knowledge or previous studies.

important role in solvent breakdown. As the name oxidative degradation suggests, it occurs when an oxidation reaction happens. This due to the presence of oxygen, oxygen containing compounds, such as NO_x and SO_x, and metal ions (Léonard et al., 2014, Vevelstad et al., 2013). Oxidative degradation primarily happens in two locations in the carbon capture process: the absorber and the rich side of the cross-heat exchanger (blue region, Fig. 2). Thus, oxidative degradation occurs at lower temperatures.

In the following sections the different oxidative degradation mechanisms, the formation of heat-stable salts (HSS), and the different degradation products will be discussed.

3.2.1. Oxidative degradation mechanisms

Identifying reaction pathways in complex systems, such as amine-based carbon capture, is challenging. Therefore, the mechanisms discussed below are proposed pathways, derived from detected degradation products and established reaction mechanisms. In general, two primary oxidative degradation mechanisms are described: electron abstraction and hydrogen abstraction (Vega et al., 2014, Fredriksen and Jens, 2013). While both pathways can produce similar degradation products, they differ in their underlying processes.

The *electron abstraction* pathway is the pathway where, as the name suggests, an electron is removed. An example of an electron abstraction pathway for MEA is illustrated in Fig. 7 (Fredriksen and Jens, 2013, Chi and Rochelle, 2002). Step (1) in Fig. 7 is the removal of an electron from the nitrogen atom of the amine group through interactions with a metal, oxygen and a metal, or a reactive free radical. This step is the rate-limiting step for the mechanism and results in the formation of an aminium radical. The aminium radical subsequently loses a proton, forming an imine radical (Step (2) in Fig. 7). The imine radical can then follow different pathways depending on the subsequent interactions. It may react with O₂, forming a peroxide radical (Step (3) in Fig. 7). The peroxide radical can further react with an unreacted amine molecule to form a peroxide (Step (4) in Fig. 7). This peroxide may react further into an imine and hydrogen peroxide, introducing a new source for radical formation into the solution (Step (5) in Fig. 7). Alternatively, the imine radical may react directly with a metal or a free radical to form an imine (Step (6) in Fig. 7). Dehydration of the imine can lead to the formation of aldehydes or ketones (in the case of α -alkyl-substituted amines) and ammonia (NH₃) (Step (7) in Fig. 7) (Crossey, 1991).

The *hydrogen abstraction (H-abstraction) pathway*, as the name implies, involves the removal of a hydrogen atom from the amine structure,

resulting in the formation of an amine radical. This process is typically initiated by free radicals, which can be generated through various mechanisms. This is shown in Fig. 8(a), where red arrows indicate a possible H-abstraction, and the black arrows indicate radical initiation. These radicals may abstract a hydrogen atom from the nitrogen atom, the α -carbon, or the β -carbon of the amine molecule.

Once formed, the amine radical can undergo internal transformations, often facilitated by the formation of a transient ring structure. This rearrangement leads to the cleavage of the N-C bond, ultimately yielding into various radicals such as aldehyde radicals, imine radicals, and amine radicals ((1), (2) and (3) in Fig. 8(b)). These radicals are the source leading to the formation of imines, aldehydes, and ammonia ((4) and (5) in Fig. 8(b) (Vega et al., 2014, Fredriksen and Jens, 2013, Goff and Rochelle, 2004)). Radicals can originate from a variety of sources, making it essential to understand these mechanisms to develop effective mitigation strategies.

Goff and Rochelle (Goff and Rochelle, 2004) suggest that H-abstraction is the primary mechanism for primary and secondary amines, as it effectively leads to the formation of amine radicals, which then contribute to further degradation. For tertiary amines, however, electron abstraction seems to be the preferred pathway. This conclusion is logical because, in tertiary amines, there is no hydrogen atom available on the nitrogen atom for abstraction. Furthermore, the formation of an internal ring structure, which is key to the hydrogen abstraction mechanism, would put significant strain on the bonds in tertiary amines. This explains why tertiary amines typically degrade through the electron abstraction mechanism rather than hydrogen abstraction during oxidative degradation (Goff and Rochelle, 2004).

Understanding whether an amine undergoes the electron abstraction mechanism, or the hydrogen abstraction mechanism is important, as the two mechanisms have different origins but also share some common features. Knowing which mechanism is at play can help in designing targeted mitigation strategies. By developing inhibitors that focus on specific aspects of each mechanism, it is possible to optimize solvent stability and better control the degradation process.

3.2.2. Formation of heat-stable salts

HSS are an important part of amine degradation products. HSS got their name because they are thermally stable salts with temperature resistance reaching up to 230 °C for organic based HSS (Crossey, 1991). They consist of both ionic and covalent combinations of an amine and an acid, forming a salt (Heat-Stable Salt - an overview 2025).

Fig. 7. Oxidative degradation via electron abstraction for MEA.

The formation of HSS arises when an amine, acting as a Brønsted base, reacts with an acid to form an amine salt (Supap et al., 2011). This acid can have two different origins. One possibility is that organic acids are formed as part of oxidative degradation pathways, as discussed in Section 3.2.1. Carboxylic acids like formic acid, acetic acid, and oxalic acid can be degradation products, which react with the amine solvent. The second source of acids is flue gas impurities such as SO_x, NO_x, and HCl, which are often present in flue gas stream (Neerup et al., 2023).

Reactions between carboxylic acids and amines typically go beyond simple acid-base reactions. Instead, more complex reaction mechanisms can occur, where HSS may act as intermediate products. For instance, when MEA reacts with formic acid, the intermediate product is a MEA salt, which then reacts further to form hydroxyethyl-formamide as shown in Fig. 9. A similar reaction occurs when MEA interacts with other carboxylic acids to form hydroxyalkyl-formamides (Supap et al., 2011, Wang and Jens, 2015).

In addition to reactions with carboxylic acids, amines react with inorganic acids, particularly when certain flue gas impurities are present e.g. O₂, NO, NO₂, SO₂, SO₃, and HCl (Emori et al., 2024). Although these impurities are typically removed before entering the absorber, traces may still be present. For instance, SO₂ oxidises to SO₃ in the presence of O₂, SO₃ reacts with water forming sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). Similarly, NO

and NO₂ react to form nitric acid (HNO₃) through a comparable oxidation process. NO can also originate from the oxidation of ammonia, a common amine degradation product, as shown in Reaction 4. This is a simplified representation, as the overall reaction can consist of one or multiple intermediate steps (Yoo et al., 2021).

The formed inorganic acids react with an amine according to Reaction 5 where X represents a strong acid anion, like sulphate, nitrate, and chloride (Neerup et al., 2023, Verma and Verma, 2009).

HSS formation is crucial in the context of solvent degradation because it has significant implications for solvent health and operational quality (Ling et al., 2019). The formation of these salts influences the solvent's ability to capture CO₂ effectively and leads to operational challenges. The impact of HSS will be further discussed below.

3.2.3. Example: oxidative degradation of AMP

Unlike MEA, AMP lacks a hydrogen atom on the carbon adjacent to the nitrogen, which makes the formation of imines through electron abstraction unlikely. Instead, AMP is believed to degrade via a hydrogen

Fig. 8. (a) Possible radical formation pathways (b) Oxidative degradation of MEA via hydrogen abstraction.

abstraction mechanism, where radicals attack the weakest C–H bonds in the molecule ((1) in Fig. 10). This results in the formation of peroxy radicals ((2) in Fig. 10), which can further decompose into compounds such as formic acid, acetone, and ammonia ((3) in Fig. 10). The degradation rate increases significantly with both oxygen partial pressure and temperature, consistent with radical-driven autoxidation mechanisms. AMP degradation has also been shown to produce specific products such as 2,4-lutidine and cyclic ureas under elevated temperature and oxygen conditions (Wang and Jens, 2012). A more detailed representation of the oxidative degradation of AMP can be seen in Fig. 10.

3.2.4. Oxidative degradation products

Table 2 provides an overview of oxidative degradation products observed in various amine-based solvents under different conditions. The degradation products include organic acids (formic acid, acetic acid, glycolic acid, and oxalic acid), aldehydes (formaldehyde), ketones (acetone), nitrogen-containing compounds (ammonia, nitrite, nitrate), and complex cyclic or amide-containing intermediates such as imidazoles and oxazolidinones. The temperature range for degradation studies varies widely (30–120°C), with oxygen partial pressure (P_{O_2}) playing a significant role in driving the oxidative pathways. Longer durations and

Fig. 9. Reaction between MEA and formic acid.

higher oxygen concentrations tend to produce a broader range of degradation products, as evidenced by studies on AMP, MEA, and PZ solvents (Wang and Jens, 2015, Thompson et al., 2014, Frimpong et al., 2013). This highlights the susceptibility of amine solvents to oxidative stress, leading to the formation of both simple and complex degradation products, which are influenced by the specific solvent, temperature, and flue gas composition.

A comparison of Tables 1 and 2 shows that some degradation products can result from both thermal and oxidative degradation mechanisms. However, oxidative degradation products are often less solvent specific in comparison with thermal degradation products. They typically consist of simpler components originating from carboxylic- and inorganic acids.

4. Solvent degradation: influences, consequences, and mitigation strategies

The mechanisms of solvent degradation can be complex, involving various chemical pathways and intermediates. This complexity implies that numerous parameters, such as solvent type, temperature, solvent composition, and the presence of impurities or metals, can significantly influence the rates at which solvents degrade. Consequently, mitigation strategies must be tailored to address specific aspects of the degradation process. For example, controlling operating conditions like stripper pressure and oxygen exposure, using inhibitors to prevent radical formation, or removing dissolved metals can all play vital roles in reducing solvent degradation and enhancing solvent stability over time.

4.1. What influences solvent stability?

Different amines exhibit varying degradation rates, largely influenced by their molecular structure and functional groups. These structural differences affect their susceptibility to thermal and oxidative degradation. In the next section, a comparative analysis of solvent stability will be discussed, providing insights into how structural characteristics impact degradation behaviour.

4.1.1. Basicity of the solvent

Thermal stability depends on both the chemical and physical properties of the solvent. One key factor is the basicity, or alkalinity, of the amine molecule. Basicity refers to an amine's ability to accept a proton (H^+) and is quantified by its pKa value (Basicity, 2024). A higher pKa indicates a stronger base. Table 3 presents the pKa₁ values of a strong acid, a strong base, and several amines used in carbon capture. Some molecules like H_2SO_4 have the possibility to lose multiple protons and

therefore have multiple pKa values, in Table 3 the pKa₁ value, which is the first dissociation constant of a molecule, is given.

As shown in Reaction 1, higher basicity allows an amine to react more easily with CO_2 , as it improves proton acceptance. However, it is also crucial to consider the nucleophilicity of the amine, which is not solely determined by its basicity. In many cases, a strong base is also a strong nucleophile, as it has a greater tendency to donate electrons. This property makes it a good attacking molecule in solvent degradation mechanisms discussed earlier in Sections 3.1 and 3.2. Consequently, nucleophilicity, which is connected to basicity, is a critical factor to evaluate when assessing solvent stability. However as can be seen in Table 3 the pKa₁ values of the different amines are closely related to each other. Other factors can also impact the nucleophilicity of a molecule which will be discussed in the next sections.

4.1.2. Impact of functional groups

To make a comparison between different functional groups, it is necessary to test compounds with the same backbone structure but different functional groups. For this purpose, Huang et al (Huang et al., 2014) evaluated the solvent stability of sodium glycinate, MEA, and ethylenediamine. Huang et al (Huang et al., 2014) concluded that the order of thermal stability, from highest to lowest, is diamines > alkanolamines > amino acid salts. The molecular structures of these compounds are shown in Fig. 11(a) (PubChem, 2024).

Amino acids degrade easily through a mechanism in which the amine group attacks the carbonyl group, forming an amide (Huang et al., 2013). This degradation occurs via a one-step reaction, which can proceed faster than the more complex mechanisms involved in the degradation of alkanolamines and diamines (Huang et al., 2014). Diamines appear to be slightly more stable than alkanolamines, even though both degrade in similar ways. This difference is not straightforward to explain. Highly reactive oxazolidinones are formed as intermediate products during the degradation of alkanolamines (Fredriksen and Jens, 2013). These intermediates react with unreacted amines, leading to the formation of dimers and eventually stable imidazolidinones. In contrast, diamines undergo a direct conversion to imidazolidinones bypassing the formation of reactive oxazolidinone intermediates (Thompson et al., 2017). This prevents further reactions between intermediates and unreacted amines (Lepaumier et al., 2009).

It is important to recognize that the stability of amines often depends on subtle details, with differences in stability frequently linked to the underlying degradation mechanism. By understanding these mechanisms, it becomes possible to compare the stability of different solvents. This knowledge could lead to potential improvements in solvent stability, either by making small adjustments to the solvent composition or

Fig. 10. Oxidative degradation of AMP.

by adding specific inhibitors.

4.1.3. Impact of amine order

Not only functional groups have an impact on solvent stability. The amine order can also have a significant impact on the degradation rate of the solvent.

An example of two amines with the same backbone structure but with a different amine order are MEA and 2-(methylamino)ethanol (MAE), whose structures are shown in Fig. 11(b). Two key factors can influence the stability of these solvents. The first is the increased steric hindrance introduced by the methyl group on the nitrogen atom. The second is the nucleophilicity of the structure.

MAE exhibits slightly greater steric hindrance due to the additional methyl group near the reactive nitrogen atom. However, MAE also has higher nucleophilicity. While MEA seems to only have a slightly lower basicity than MAE (as indicated by their pKa values), MAE is more nucleophilic because of the electron-donating effect of the second methyl group on the nitrogen atom. This effect increases the availability

of the nitrogen atom in MAE for nucleophilic attacks (Lepaumier et al., 2009).

Based on experimental results, Huang et al. concluded that MEA is more stable than its corresponding secondary amine, MAE. Although MAE has greater steric hindrance compared to MEA, its higher nucleophilicity appears to play a more significant role in the degradation mechanisms, leading to reduced stability. Similar conclusions were drawn for other functional amines (Huang et al., 2014).

4.1.4. Steric effect

Steric effects can influence solvent stability. To test this, a more branched amine with the same degree of substitution can be used, as this may affect the nucleophilicity of the amine. A good example for this comparison is the two primary amines MEA and AMP, which are shown in Fig. 11(c) (PubChem, 2024).

Huang et al. (Huang et al., 2014) tested the thermal stability of these solvents and concluded that AMP is more stable than MEA in degradation experiments. This is due to the two methyl groups on the α -carbon,

Table 2
Overview of oxidative degradation products discussed in literature.

Reference	Solvent	Degradation products	T [°C]/P [barg]	Flue gas composition	Duration of degradation	Detection method
Campbell et al (Campbell et al., Nov. 25, 2022).	AMP	Acetone Acetic acid Ammonia Nitrate Nitrite 2,4- lutidine	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	GC, GC-FID
Wang et al (Wang and Jens, 2015).*	5m AMP	Ammonia Formate Acetate Glycolate Oxalate Nitrite Nitrate Acetone Acetone oxime 4,4-Dimethyl-2-Oxazolidinone (DMOZD) 2,4-Lutidine Formamide Acetamide N- (1,1-Dimethyl-2-hydroxyethyl)formamide	80 –120/N. M.	P _{O2} = 250 kPa**	13 weeks	IC, GC-MS
Léonard et al. (Lab scale) (Léonard et al., 2014)	7 m MEA	N- (2-hydroxyethyl)imidazole (HEI) 4- (2-hydroxyethyl) piperazine-2-one (HEPO) N,N'-bis (2-hydroxyethyl) oxamide (BHEOX) 2-oxazolidinone (OZD) Ammonia	120/4	5% O ₂ , 15% CO ₂ , 80% N ₂	1 week	HPLC, GC, FTIR
Thompson et al (Thompson et al., 2014, Frimpong et al., 2013). (Pilot plant)	7 m MEA	Formate (799 ppm) Chloride (40 ppm) Nitrite (<3 ppm) Nitrate (720 ppm) Sulphate (3400 ppm) Thiosulfate (67 ppm)	30-45/atm. (Absorber)	6% O ₂ , 14% CO ₂ , 250 ppm SO ₂ , 90 ppm NO _x	100 hours	IC
Campbell et al (Campbell et al., Nov. 25, 2022).	PZ	Oxalic acid Ethylene diamine (EDA) Glycine Glycolic acid 2-oxopiperazine (OPZ) Carboxylic acid Formaldehyde Formic acid Acetate Acetyl piperazine (APZ) Mono-nitrosopiperazine (MNPZ)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	GC, GC-FID
Freeman S (Freeman, 2024).	8 m PZ	Glycolate Oxalate Acetate Formate Ethylenediamine (EDA) 1-Formylpiperazine (FPZ) Nitrite Nitrate	55-70/N.M.	P _{O2} = 40 –98 kPa**	350 hours	IC, IC-MS, NMR, HPLC, LC-MS, AA-LC

*Temperature accelerated oxidative degradation

**Elevated O₂ partial pressure used for lab-based experiments

N.A.: Not Applicable –degradation products mentioned based on theoretical knowledge or previous studies.

N.M.: Not Mentioned –parameter not mentioned by article.

Table 3
pK_a values of given compounds.

Compound	pKa1 value	Reference
H2SO4	-3	(Table SevenPointTwo, 2024)
NaOH	15	(Boonekamp et al., 2018)
MEA	9.5	(PubChem, 2024)
EDA	10.0	(PubChem, 2024)
AMP	9.7	(PubChem, 2024)
PZ	9.7	(PubChem, 2024)
1,2-DAP (1,2-diaminopropane)	10.0	(PubChem, 2024)

which create steric hindrance for an attacking molecule to be able to attack the α -carbon of the amine. After MEA and AMP react with CO₂ to form MEA- and AMP carbamate internal cyclization reactions are less likely to occur in the AMP carbamate compared to the MEA carbamate. This is because the presence of the two methyl groups in AMP causes greater electron repulsion than in MEA, reducing the stability of the carbamate and increasing strain in potential oxazolidinone-like structures (Huang et al., 2014).

In conclusion, the stability of primary amines follows this order: diamines > alkanolamines > amino acid salts (Huang et al., 2014). For

Fig. 11. (a) Different 2-carbon amines (b) Structure of MEA and MAE (c) Structure of MEA and AMP.

both alkanolamines and diamines, primary amines degrade slower than secondary amines due to the lower nucleophilicity of primary amines. Additionally, steric hindrance around the amine group appears to improve solvent stability.

4.2. Effect of dissolved metals

As mentioned in Section 3.2.1, dissolved metals play a significant role in solvent degradation, particularly in oxidative degradation.

Metals in a carbon capture plant typically originate from two sources: fly ash and corrosion of equipment, with the latter being the most significant contributor (Yuan et al., 2023, Dhingra et al., May 2017). Metals impact oxidative degradation in two main ways. First, they can act as an electron acceptor and influence the electron abstraction mechanism. Second, metals catalyse the formation of radicals, which are crucial in the hydrogen abstraction mechanism. Therefore, the greater the concentration of metals in the solution, the more oxidative degradation occurs. As oxidative degradation increases, more corrosive degradation products are formed. This, in turn, leads to more metals being leached into the solvent, further accelerating oxidative degradation. In conclusion, oxidative degradation is an autocatalytic process (Léonard et al., 2014, Chi and Rochelle, 2002, Dhingra et al., 2017).

Léonard et al (Léonard et al., 2014) quantitatively tested the effect of dissolved metals on solvent degradation. To simulate industrial conditions, stainless steel metal elements: iron, chromium, nickel, and manganese were added to the solvent at relevant concentrations, as shown in Table 4. The presence of metal compounds led to a 58 % increase in MEA degradation compared to an experiment without metals (Léonard et al., 2014).

Metals did not affect the overall thermal stability of the solvent, thus this increase was due to an increase in oxidative degradation (Léonard

Table 4

Metal concentrations used in the oxidative degradation of MEA by Léonard et al (Léonard et al., 2014).

Metal	Concentration [ppm]
Iron (Fe^{2+})	52.8
Chromium (Cr^{3+})	1.4
Nickel (Ni^{2+})	5.3
Manganese (Mn^{2+})	1.4

et al., 2014). In pilot plant studies, iron concentrations typically increase steadily from 0 to around 900 hours of operation (Thompson et al., 2017). However, beyond a critical number of operating hours the iron concentration appears to rise exponentially. The exact cause of this phenomenon is not yet fully understood. One possible explanation is that oxidative degradation is an autocatalytic process, in which metals act as catalysts. Since metals facilitate oxidative degradation, solvent degradation accelerates over time, accelerating metal dissolution, leading to the observed exponential increase in iron concentration (Rieder and Unterberger, 2013).

Sexton (Sexton, 2024) conducted similar experiments to examine the effect of metals, focusing on individual metal species and combinations. The degradation of MEA in the presence of 1 mM iron (56.7 ppm Fe^{2+}) served as the base case. Vanadium, a mixture of chromium and nickel, and a mixture of iron and copper were tested. Copper is commonly used as a corrosion inhibitor, so it is important to understand its impact on solvent degradation. Based on the results, it could be concluded that the oxidation potential of the tested metals followed the order: $Fe/Cu > Cr/Ni > Fe > V$ (Sexton, 2024).

In addition to catalysing oxidative degradation, dissolved metals can form complexes with the amine molecules themselves. While this

complexation does not constitute a degradation mechanism, it can reduce the available free amine for CO₂ absorption, lowering the solvent's capture capacity. However, some studies suggest that certain amine-metal complexes may improve solvent regeneration characteristics, facilitate desorption and reduce energy consumption. The overall impact of complex formation depends on the specific metal ions present and the solvent chemistry (Cheng et al., 2018).

Copper-based corrosion inhibitors may be used with the good intention of reducing equipment corrosion, but they would significantly increase oxidative degradation. As a result, corrosion rates might unexpectedly rise, leaving operators uncertain about the cause. This highlights the importance of understanding the interaction between metals and oxidative degradation to prevent unintended consequences.

4.3. Influences of operational conditions on solvent degradation

Factors such as temperature, flue gas composition, and CO₂ loading play a critical role in determining the rate and pathway of solvent degradation. This section discusses how these operational parameters shape the degradation behaviour of solvents in real-world carbon capture systems.

4.3.1. Oxygen and gas composition

Oxygen acts as a key initiator of free radical chain reactions by forming reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydroxyl (•OH) and hydroperoxyl (•OOH) radicals. These radicals attack the amine solvent and catalyse a cascade of oxidative degradation reactions. Consequently, the concentration of oxygen in the flue gas is a key driver for solvent stability in post-combustion CO₂ capture systems.

Degradation experiments using monoethanolamine (MEA) have shown that increasing the oxygen concentration from 5 % to 10 % can increase the degradation rate by as much as 160 % (Léonard et al., 2014). This underscores the sensitivity of oxidative degradation to oxygen levels. The composition of flue gas varies significantly between sources, not only in terms of oxygen concentration but also in the presence of impurities such as NO_x and SO_x, which further contribute to solvent degradation through the formation of nitrosamines, nitramines, and heat-stable salts. These compositional differences influence both the rate of oxidative degradation and the choice of mitigation strategies. An overview of typical flue gas characteristics is provided in Table 5.

Given these risks, it is crucial to characterize the flue gas composition before plant startup. Installing gas composition analysers can support real-time monitoring and control. In high-risk applications, gas pre-treatment units such as de-dusting filters, or desulfurization stages may be considered (Dai et al., 2019).

Ultimately, solvent selection should consider the oxidative environment of the capture site. For example, using MEA in high-oxygen flue gas sources like cement plants may lead to excessive degradation and operational instability unless compensated with strong mitigation strategies. In such cases, more oxidation-resistant solvents (e.g., CESAR1) or solvent blends designed for oxidative environments may be more suitable.

4.3.2. CO₂ loading

As mentioned in the previous sections, CO₂ plays a key role in thermal degradation. Lean amines are relatively stable at higher

Table 5
Flue gas composition of cement- and NGCC flue gas.

Flue Gas Source	O ₂ % (Amann and Bouallou, 2009, Bosoaga et al., 2009)	NO _x /SO _x content (EPA, 2025, Dai et al., 2019)	Oxidative Degradation Risk
Cement plant	8 - 14	Medium	High
NGCC	3 - 6	Low	Moderate

temperatures, whereas loaded amines degrade through the pathways outlined above. However, CO₂ loading also affects oxidative degradation.

Research by Høisæter et al (Høisæter et al., 2022) shows that amine loss increases almost linearly with CO₂ loading. This is illustrated in Fig. 12 where the relative amount of amine left (%) can be seen in the y-axis and decreases linearly with increasing loading presented on the x-axis.

This highlights the importance of finding a balance between longer contact times in the absorber, favourable for efficient CO₂ absorption, and the risk of increased solvent degradation due to increased loading.

CO₂ loading appears to inhibit the oxidative degradation of certain amines to some extent (Léonard et al., 2014). The effect of the CO₂ concentration on the inhibition is unclear, since studies report contradicting results. Some studies suggest that the inhibition effect is independent from the CO₂ concentration (Léonard et al., 2014). Other studies clearly observe a decrease in oxidative degradation with increased CO₂ concentration (Supap et al., 2009).

Concluding, CO₂ loading has a complex influence on both thermal and oxidative degradation. While it promotes thermal degradation in loaded amines, it can also suppress oxidative degradation, showing the need for careful control of operating conditions. Still, the negative impact on thermal stability appears to outweigh the positive effect on oxidative degradation. Overall, this means that higher CO₂ content leads to increased solvent degradation.

4.3.3. Temperature and pressure

Temperature and pressure have a strong influence on degradation kinetics. However, temperature changes affect the processes in the absorber and stripper differently. Besides degradation, temperature also impacts other important processes such as absorption kinetics, stripping efficiency, and overall energy consumption. Pressure is the key operational parameter in a CO₂ capture plant; however, many studies use temperature as the main operational parameter in degradation experiments and therefore the two are mentioned together.

As researched by (Løge et al., 2025) increasing the stripper pressure improves capture efficiency, reduces lean solvent loading, and increases the solvent's cyclic capacity. However, increasing the stripper pressure from 1 bara to 2 bara results in a threefold increase in the degradation rate (Løge et al., 2025). An increase in stripper pressure naturally leads to a higher temperature. Raising the temperature at constant pressure from 110 °C to 150 °C results in an increase in amine loss from around 3 % to 45 % (Buvik et al., 2025). However, the work of Moser et al (Moser et al., 2025) shows that higher temperatures do not lead to more oxidative degradation products. This suggests that the increase in degradation observed at higher stripper pressure is mainly due to thermal degradation, which is to be expected.

Not only the stripper pressure can be adjusted; the absorber

Fig. 12. Relation between amine loss and amine loading (Høisæter et al., 2022).

temperature can also be regulated using advanced configurations such as intercooling, which has been investigated in recent studies (Dimitriadi et al., 2025). Research by Dimitriadi et al (Dimitriadi et al., 2025) showed that intercooling reduces the temperature in the top section of the absorber by about 35 °C at the height where the intercooler is installed. The main goal of intercooling is to lower the temperature to enhance the absorption process (Taipabu et al., 2023). Interestingly, implementing intercooling led to an 80 % reduction in ammonia emissions from the absorber (Dimitriadi et al., 2025). This suggests a decrease in oxidative degradation, as ammonia is mainly formed through this pathway. However, a critical point should be considered: while lower absorber temperatures may reduce oxidative degradation, they also increase the solvent loading. As discussed in Section 4.3.2, this can lead to higher thermal degradation in the stripper. More research on the effect of advanced configurations on solvent degradation is therefore necessary.

In summary, temperature and pressure play a critical role in both solvent degradation and process performance, but their effects vary between the absorber and stripper. While advanced configurations like intercooling show potential to reduce oxidative degradation, they may shift the degradation issues to the stripper, highlighting the need for further research on their overall impact.

4.4. Important industrial consequences of solvent degradation

Solvent degradation is being studied increasingly due to its significant consequences on the overall carbon capture process sustainability. It leads to higher energy consumption and changes in solvent composition, which affect its properties. Heat-stable salts (HSS) play a key role in this process. This section will discuss the most important consequences of solvent degradation.

4.4.1. Increased energy consumption

Solvent degradation and energy consumption in a carbon capture process are closely interconnected. An ideal solvent should not only have a large CO₂ absorption capacity and fast absorption kinetics, but also a good stability at high temperatures and CO₂ loadings. The more stable a solvent is, the higher the stripper pressure can be. Higher stripper pressures increase the thermal compression in the stripper, which is more efficient than mechanical compression through the compressor (Davis and Rochelle, 2009). Additionally, higher stripper pressure allows for a downsizing of both the stripper and the compressor, reducing the overall size and cost of the equipment (Davis and Rochelle, 2009). In conclusion, a solvent that is more degradation resistant allows for higher stripper pressures which can be overall cost reducing (Rochelle, 2012).

Davis (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024) determined that the equivalent work

Fig. 13. (a) The influence of the stripper pressure on the equivalent work and MEA loss (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024) (b) Determination of the optimum stripper pressure according to Davis (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024).

(W_{eq}), which includes reboiler duty (Q_i), compression work ($W_{compress}$), and pump work (W_{pump}), depends on the reboiler temperature (T_i) and the ambient temperature (T_{sink}) as shown in Eq. 6.

$$W_{eq} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{reboilers}} 0.75 \times Q_i \left(\frac{T_i + 5 - T_{sink}}{T_i + 5} \right) + W_{pump} + W_{compress} \quad (6)$$

Davis (Davis, 2024) demonstrated that the equivalent work decreases exponentially with increasing stripper pressure, as can be seen by the blue curve in Fig. 13(a). However, the loss of MEA also increases exponentially with rising pressure, as proved by the green curve in Fig. 13(a).

Both energy requirements and MEA loss contribute to operational cost. This concept is illustrated in Fig. 13(b) for a 7 m MEA system with optimized lean loading for each stripper pressure (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024). The green curve represents the MEA loss cost, the blue line the energy cost related to the equivalent work, and these two costs give rise to a total cost, represented by the red line. By finding the minimum of the total cost an optimal stripper pressure and can be determined (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024). For this configuration a stripper pressure of 3.6 atm. would be the most cost-efficient stripper pressure, as found by Davis (Davis, Oct. 23, 2024). This stripper pressure is determined based on Aspen Plus simulations, however in reality the stripper pressure will be maintained around 2–2.5 atm (Løge et al., 2025). Real life pilot plant data also confirms this idea that higher stripper pressure reduces energy demand and compression work but increases solvent degradation (Løge et al., 2025).

When considering solvent selection and cost, solvent degradation plays a critical role in the techno-economic analysis. Ding et al (Ding et al., 2023) performed a techno-economic analysis of various MEA blends to assess which blend is the most cost-effective. Some solvents, such as PZ, have higher thermal stability but come with higher costs. Therefore, calculating cost-effectiveness is essential to determine the most economical solvent for operation.

In conclusion, the operating pressure of the stripper is highly influenced by the solvent used and its thermal degradation properties. The stripper pressure must strike a balance: it needs to be high enough to enable efficient thermal compression but not so high that it increases energy consumption and accelerates solvent degradation, leading to costly reclamation. Additionally, solvent cost and solvent stability must be carefully balanced and evaluated to optimize overall cost-effectiveness. Solvent degradation has a significant impact on techno-economic performance of a CC setup.

4.4.2. Damage to equipment

One of the most significant effects of solvent degradation is the accelerated corrosion, primarily caused by the formation of HSS. It has been shown that an increase in HSS contributes to a higher corrosion rate, which in turn leads to several negative effects (Emori et al., 2023). Corrosion damages the installation and raises the concentration of iron carbonate, potentially resulting in foaming and fouling. These issues ultimately increase costs and decrease the overall efficiency of the process. In addition to corrosion, the precipitation of HSS can also lead to equipment erosion.

4.4.3. Foaming

Foaming can be caused by various factors, one of which is solvent degradation. Mansoori et al. (2022) found that an increase in HSS concentration leads to foaming (Mansoori et al., 2022). Foaming not only increases the risk of column flooding but also contributes to pressure loss and reduced mass transfer due to changes in surface tension properties, which affect the gas/liquid interface. As a result, foaming has negative effects on both operating conditions and overall capture efficiency (Verma and Verma, 2009, Jorsboe et al., 2022).

4.4.4. Change in physicochemical properties of the solvent

The formation of degradation products significantly influences the composition and, consequently, the physicochemical properties of the solvent. Degradation products typically increase both the density and viscosity of the solvent. As a result, more power is required to circulate the solution, due to a decrease in heat and mass transfer caused by these property changes (Ling et al., 2019). The Einstein-Stokes-Sutherland equation can be seen in Eq. 7 where D: Diffusion coefficient [m^2/s], T: Temperature [K], η : Dynamic viscosity [Pa.s], and r: radius of the diffusing molecule [m]. As can be seen in Eq. 7 the viscosity is inversely proportional to the diffusion coefficient for molecular diffusion in liquids, explained by the Einstein-Stokes-Sutherland equation (Ishii et al., 2022). The same can be said for heat transfer, where in Eq. 8 the Prandtl number shows the proportional relationship between the Prandtl number and the viscosity of the liquid (Prandtl Number, 2025). Where in Eq. 8 Pr: Prandtl number, c_p : Specific heat capacity [J/(kg.K)], η : Dynamic viscosity [Pa.s], and k: Heat conductivity [W/(m.K)]. An increase in viscosity leads to an increase in Prandtl number, which means that heat diffusion becomes less efficient relative to momentum diffusion. Decreasing the overall heat transfer in the liquid.

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (7)$$

$$Pr = \frac{\eta c_p}{k} \quad (8)$$

Besides a decrease in mass- and heat transfer HSS can also precipitate, leading to fouling and plugging of equipment. In heat exchangers, for example, the presence of HSS can cause a significant decrease in heat transfer efficiency (Emori et al., 2023, Berce et al., 2021).

Overall, these effects contribute to higher operation costs and reduced operational efficiency, highlighting the urgent need to try and mitigate solvent degradation.

4.5. Mitigation strategies for solvent degradation

Now that the negative impact of solvent degradation on the process is clear, it is important to explore strategies to avoid or slow down degradation. One approach is the use of inhibitors or reclaiming the solvent at the appropriate time. These strategies will be discussed in this section.

4.5.1. The use of solvent degradation inhibitors

Controlling corrosion and oxidative degradation is crucial, and one effective approach is the use of degradation inhibitors. Generally, there are three types of inhibitors, each targeting a different aspect of the oxidative degradation mechanism (Léonard, 2025). The first type is chelating agents, which form complexes with dissolved metals, preventing these metals from catalysing oxidative degradation.

The second type of inhibitors are radical and O_2 scavengers. These inhibitors react with radicals to form stable products, effectively halting the chain reactions. Unlike chelating agents, however, they are consumed during operation and must be replenished. The final type includes both organic and inorganic salts. These salts increase the ionic strength of the solution, reducing gas solubility and consequently the concentration of O_2 in the solvent, which lowers oxidative degradation. However, salts can also negatively impact corrosion, thereby contributing to degradation. Overall, chelating agents and scavenger inhibitors are primarily used to prevent solvent degradation.

Table 6 provides an overview of commonly used inhibitors for mitigating solvent degradation, categorized by their type: chelating agents and radical/ O_2 scavengers. Each entry specifies the inhibitor's name, abbreviation (if applicable), and its function in preventing degradation. This is relevant since selecting the appropriate inhibitor type is critical to reducing the catalysing effects of dissolved metals or oxidative stress in solvent systems, improving the longevity of carbon

Table 6
Different solvent degradation inhibitors and their structures.

Name (Abbreviation)	Structure	Type
Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)		Chelating agent
1-hydroxyethylidene diphosphonic acid (HEDP)		Chelating agent
Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA)		Chelating agent
2,2'-thiodiethanol (TDE)		Radical/O ₂ scavenger
3,3'-Dithiodipropionic acid (DTDP)		Radical/O ₂ scavenger
2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (DMTD)		Radical/O ₂ scavenger
Inhibitor A	KI (Fytianos et al., 2016; Goff, 2024; Plantz and Rochelle, 2022)	Radical/O ₂ scavenger

capture solvents (Léonard et al., 2014). The inhibitors that are shown in Table 6 are known inhibitors and their structures are given in the second column. One of them is inhibitor A, an inhibitor developed by The University of Texas at Austin (Goff, 2024) and is used in various research articles (Léonard, 2025, Freeman et al., 2010). Inhibitor A was later

identified as potassium iodide (KI) (Plantz and Rochelle, 2022).

Léonard et al (Léonard et al., 2014) tested different inhibitors in oxidative degradation experiments at temperatures between 50 and 80 °C in the presence of oxygen. The same concentration of metals listed in Table 4 were used during the tests. Overall, inhibitor A and DMTD

showed the best results in slowing down oxidative degradation (Léonard, 2025).

Inhibitors not only affect the oxidative degradation rate but can also influence the thermal degradation rate. For example, DMTD, which showed promising results in lowering oxidative degradation, appeared to lower the thermal stability of the solvent, making it less suitable for implementation. On the other hand, inhibitor A did not affect the thermal stability of the solvent, making it a better candidate. This highlights the importance of considering all aspects of solvent degradation when evaluating inhibitors or other mitigation strategies.

In conclusion, an ideal inhibitor must reduce oxidative degradation, not reduce thermal stability, and not enhance corrosion. Inhibitor A appears to meet all these criteria and operates most effectively (Léonard et al., 2014, Fytianos et al., 2016, Léonard, 2025). However, when exposed to temperature cycling, the inhibitor lost its inhibition properties, highlighting the importance of testing inhibitors under fully simulated industrial conditions (Plantz and Rochelle, 2022).

4.5.2. Reclamation of the solvent

Solvent degradation has significant consequences and can severely impact the efficiency and operability of the carbon capture process. To ensure smooth and continuous operation, it is necessary to restore the solvent to its 'original' condition over time. Several techniques are available for solvent reclamation, each focusing on different aspects, such as removing HSS or restoring the overall solvent matrix.

4.5.3. Thermal reclamation

Thermal reclamation is the most used method for treating degraded solvent across various industries. In this process, the solvent is mixed with a high concentration of caustic soda (NaOH) and heated to high temperatures (typically around 130°C) using high-pressure steam. This causes the amines and water to boil off, leaving the degradation products, including HSS, metals, and other by-products, in the reclaimer where they form a sludge. This sludge requires careful handling due to safety and environmental concerns. Thermal reclamation can be performed in batch or continuous modes, depending on the process configuration (Campbell et al., 2022, Thermal Reclamation - an overview 2024).

4.5.4. Ion exchange

Unlike thermal reclamation, ion exchange focuses on removing HSS from the solvent. This technique uses a packed bed of ion exchange resin to adsorb HSS. Typically, an alkaline resin (R-OH) is used to 'neutralize' the salts via a strong acid-strong base reaction. Process conditions are critical, as ion exchange resins are sensitive to thermal degradation and lose effectiveness at high temperatures. Besides that, resins need to be regenerated over time, often a lead-lag-regeneration configuration with three ion exchange columns is used to ensure continuous operation is possible. However, ion exchange does not remove all non-ionic degradation products, and over time, an alternative reclamation method may be necessary.

4.5.5. Other techniques

While thermal reclamation and ion exchange are very useful techniques, other techniques like electrodialysis, electromagnetic separation, and solvent extraction are also used (Vega et al., 2014, Bazhenov et al., 2014). Researchers are continuously exploring more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly reclamation methods to improve solvent recovery (Abad et al., 2024, PatentPak, 2025).

4.6. Implications of degradation mechanisms for solvent selection

The mechanisms and influencing factors discussed in the previous sections underscore that solvent selection should not be based solely on absorption efficiency, but also on chemical stability under site-specific operating conditions and the ability to manage degradation-related

challenges

Primary amines such as MEA are highly reactive with CO₂ and offer fast absorption rates but are particularly susceptible to both thermal and oxidative degradation (Gibbins, 2024). This results in high solvent loss, increased formation of heat-stable salts, and a need for more frequent solvent reclaiming or replacement. While MEA remains a benchmark solvent, its high degradation rate makes it less favourable for systems with high oxygen concentrations or high regeneration temperatures.

Secondary amines such as DEA show slightly improved stability, while tertiary amines like MDEA are more resistant to thermal degradation due to their structure (de Ávila et al., 2015). AMP, a sterically hindered primary amine, shows moderate degradation behaviour and is less prone to form imines, suggesting a slightly different oxidative pathway. However, AMP has a low rate of CO₂ absorption, so it is of interest to combine it with an amine with high rate of CO₂ absorption, like PZ (Zhang et al., 2017).

Piperazine (PZ) blends like CESAR1 demonstrate relatively good resistance to oxidative degradation and have been tested extensively (Mazari et al., 2014). However, the formation of cyclic degradation products and precipitation risks still require attention (Neerup et al., 2025). These systems may offer a more stable performance in oxygen-rich environments, such as cement flue gases, but the potential for solid formation and fouling needs to be managed.

Ultimately, solvent selection should consider:

- Flue gas composition (e.g., O₂ and NO_x levels)
- Operating conditions (e.g., stripper pressure)
- Toxicity and degradation product handling
- Reclaiming and maintenance costs
- Regulatory requirements on emissions (e.g., nitrosamines)

Understanding the degradation mechanisms is essential for making informed trade-offs between solvent performance and long-term process stability. As new solvents are developed, degradation resistance under real operating conditions should be a key design criterion alongside absorption efficiency.

5. State of the art solvents and future work

Ongoing research is continuously working to make carbon capture more cost-effective and environmentally efficient. This includes both optimizing existing technologies and developing new ones. In this section, state-of-the-art technologies currently being researched, as well as the gaps that still need to be filled for further advancement will be discussed.

5.1. Development of new solvents

The development of new solvents for CO₂ capture is a key focus area to improve both the efficiency and environmental sustainability of carbon capture processes. While ionic liquids (ILs) were initially considered promising due to their high CO₂ absorption capacity, they face challenges such as high costs, complex synthesis, toxicity, and poor biodegradability (Ionic liquid, 2024). This has driven the exploration of alternatives like deep eutectic solvents (DESSs), which offer several advantages over ILs. DESSs are formed by combining hydrogen-donating and hydrogen-accepting components, typically acids and bases, through hydrogen bonding. They are low-cost, simpler to synthesize, free from unwanted byproducts, and biodegradable (Foorginezhad and Ji, 2024).

Despite their potential, many DESSs have a high viscosity, which can limit their practical application. To overcome this, DESSs are often modified with other chemical compounds to reduce viscosity. One promising example is the DES composed of MEACl and EDA, known as [MEACl,EDA]. MEACl is an MEA salt that is prepared using a dropwise addition of HCl and MEA in an equimolar amount, as in detail described

by Trivedi et al (Trivedi et al., 2016).. This solvent has demonstrated a significant improvement in CO₂ absorption capacity compared to traditional solvents like MEA. At a concentration of 40 wt.%, it exhibits an absorption capacity of 22.09 wt.% CO₂, which is notably higher than MEA's absorption capacity of 15.74 wt.%. However, the viscosity of [MEACL,EDA] increased after CO₂ absorption, from 4.4 mPa·s to 13.3 mPa·s. In comparison, MEA shows a less significant increase in viscosity under similar conditions. Promising is that the [MEACL,EDA] solvent showed 88 % regeneration efficiency after five cycles, with no structural cleavage, indicating its potential as a stable and effective alternative for CO₂ capture applications.

This development of DESs, particularly [MEACL,EDA], shows promise for advancing CO₂ capture technology, though further improvements in viscosity and long-term stability will be essential for broader implementation.

In addition to the development of deep eutectic solvents (DESs), nanotechnology is also being explored to create high-capacity CO₂ absorbent solvents that are resistant to oxidative degradation (Willis et al., 2013). A recent study by K. Vardanjani (Vardanjani, May 18, 2023) combines novel components and the implementation of nanotechnology into solvents to improve solvent performance. The results from amine degradation experiments (72 h) indicate that heat-stable salts (HSS) remained below 2 %, suggesting that the solvent is resistant to oxidative degradation. However, there are possible improvements in the study of K. Vardanjani (Vardanjani, 2023). The exact conditions under which the oxidative degradation experiments were conducted are not provided and no experiments were conducted to assess the thermal stability of the solvent. However, this is needed for complete understanding its performance under typical CO₂ capture process conditions.

While this nanotechnology-based solvent is promising in terms of oxidative degradation resistance, further research is needed assess its thermal stability to determine its suitability for industrial CO₂ capture processes.

5.2. Recommendations for solvent management

Amine-based carbon capture is still one of the most widely used technologies to capture CO₂ from various sources, but its high energy consumption during solvent regeneration has prompted the development of alternative technologies. While these new methods show promise, it will take time for them to be fully optimized and competitive with amine-based systems. Therefore, continuing research into improving the existing amine-based carbon capture technology is crucial.

Solvent health monitoring is essential to ensure the effectiveness of prevention techniques and control solvent degradation. Currently, solvent degradation has primarily been studied in an "offline" manner, where samples are degraded under controlled conditions in a laboratory or pilot scale experiment, and then analysed using different analytical techniques as shown in Tables 1 and 2. While this approach provides valuable data over extended periods, it does not allow for rapid response to changes in the process or enable real-time monitoring of mitigation strategies. This highlights the need for "online" and "inline" monitoring of solvent degradation to track its progress continuously during operation. Real-time monitoring can help optimize process control, provide better insights into the effectiveness of mitigation strategies, and improve the timing for solvent reclamation.

Recent studies have begun exploring techniques like FTIR to track solvent degradation in real-time by quantifying changes in solvent properties such as total alkalinity and organic carbon content (Wagaarachchige et al., 2024). Multivariate data analysis methods like Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS-R) have also been applied to predict solvent degradation based on these measurements. However, the complexity of the data analysis and the overall process remain a challenge. More research is required to refine these methods for practical

application.

Once effective solvent monitoring is in place, prevention and control measures can be more efficiently optimized. By continuously tracking solvent health, strategies such as the use of novel solvents, degradation inhibitors, oxygen removal, and solvent reclamation can be better controlled during operation, leading to significant improvements in the efficiency of the carbon capture process.

Ultimately advancing real-time monitoring of solvent degradation, along with further research into prevention and control techniques, is key to improving the sustainability and economic viability of amine-based carbon capture technologies in the long term.

6. Conclusion

Solvent degradation remains one of the key operational and economic challenges in amine-based carbon capture systems. This review has clarified both thermal and oxidative degradation mechanisms, showing how factors such as oxygen concentration, CO₂ loading, temperature, pressure, and dissolved metals influence degradation. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for implementing effective mitigation strategies and ensuring stable long-term operation.

The formation of heat-stable salts (HSS), increased corrosion-driven metal release, and solvent property shifts underline the need for robust monitoring and proactive solvent management. Advanced analytical techniques, including real-time solvent health monitoring, alongside the application of degradation inhibitors and efficient solvent reclamation, are necessary to maintain process efficiency. In addition, more research is needed on the interaction between thermal and oxidative degradation under pilot-scale conditions, as this remains insufficiently understood but is highly relevant for further understanding of degradation mechanisms.

Looking forward, innovative solvent systems, such as deep eutectic solvents and nanotechnology-based absorbents, present opportunities to enhance chemical stability. However, their degradation behaviour under industrial conditions must be better understood. Future research should focus on integrating these novel solvents, improving monitoring techniques, and addressing site-specific operational impacts to optimize both solvent stability and overall capture performance.

Through continued innovation and deeper understanding of degradation processes, amine-based carbon capture can remain a cornerstone technology in the global effort to reduce CO₂ emissions.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used GPT-4o by OpenAI to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ward Peeters: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Randi Neerup:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Philip L. Fosbøl:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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